

If Artists Were Given more Opportunities, would they have a Better Chance at Financial Viability?

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Abstract:- Art helps people to express themselves, it speaks to people in a way that words definitely cannot. Whether it's fine art like painting and sculpting or performance art like theater, dance, or music, it has a deep influence on both the artist and the viewer and acts as an effective stress reliever. Art forms like music, literature, etc. have a great impact on our mental health making us feel more optimistic and relaxed. Despite this fact, thousands of artists don't get the opportunities they deserve. Since they are unable to showcase their work and reach out to audiences, their hard work and talent remain unappreciated due to which they fail to make their work financially viable. Consequently, people don't pursue arts as a career due to the fear that they wouldn't be able to make a satisfactory income. However, artists have made progress in recent years with the emergence and growth of media and technology. For example, the film and music industry is huge but there are hundreds of artists who are extremely talented but are still struggling to get an opportunity in these fields. In other words, artists are not given the opportunities they deserve and hence they are unable to make their work financially viable.

I. LITERATURE

The literature has identified the economic impact of art and how it is a major contributor to economic vitality. It also studies the growth of productivity and earnings of the regional economy due to the presence of art (Markusen and King, 2003). This is a unique industry and the literature also talks about the high self-employment rate of artists, the important role that they play in urban economies, and how they have a great potential to lead in social and urban transformation (Markusen, 2006, 38(10), 1921-1940). However, very little attention has been paid to artists and their artistic/ creative endeavors and studies the importance of art and artists in their community and social life and how we are still unaware of the diversity, contribution, goals, etc. of these artists (Jackson, 2004, 34(1), 43-58 and Caves, 2000, No. 20). This is a gap I wish to fill through my research.

The literature has extensively explored the barriers and challenges faced by artists and how they can overcome these hardships. For example, the literature studies failure in the

creative field and how these failures can be overcome. Creativity support tools as examples of the potential value of supporting activities (Kim, Bagla, and Bernstein, 2015, pp.157-160). It speaks about the boundaries which hamper innovation in the art world, the role of amphibious artists in bridging the gaps as well as ways in which we can link artists to those who consume their products. (Patriotta and Hirsch, 2016, 37(6), 867-887). It speaks about how the means of providing and marketing professional artistic services is a good business. It also talks about the potential sources of market failure and how artistic performances have a feature of a natural monopoly. (Adler, 2006). It focuses on the exceptional economy of arts and how artists earn very little. Although art operates successfully in its marketplace, artists are unable to make a satisfactory income and require subsidies to grow their income. (Abbing, 2008, p. 368). My research is based on performance and fine artists in Kolkata. Through both primary and secondary research I will find out if they are given more opportunities to showcase their work, would they have a better chance at financial viability? The literature speaks about the lack of opportunities and financial viability for artists and I wish to elaborate on these themes. I wish to contribute to the present literature and take it forward by proving that this issue is prevalent in my region as well. I will also be elaborating more clearly on the research question and try to find any missing patterns which have not been studied yet.

II. METHODS

I will be conducting my research by interviewing struggling artists and asking them about what it is that they think is stopping them from becoming successful, their goals and expectations, and their reasons for choosing arts as a career. In addition to this, I will also speak to established artists to find out how they have made their careers financially viable and how they reached the positions they are in now, why they have chosen this path, do they think all artists currently get equal opportunities and if luck is an important factor in this highly competitive field. Speaking to both sides will give me a good idea of what the art industry is currently lacking and what should be done to help more artists. One of the reasons for doing qualitative research is that this method implicitly assumes a richness of data because a case study is intended to examine a phenomenon in its real-life context (Yin, R.K, 2000, pp. 185-193) I believe that conducting interviews will help me gain

more insight into this topic and learn about the views of artists who are going through this issue. Moreover, I will be conducting secondary research to gain more information on how performance and fine artists can make their careers financially viable. I will do this by going through the research done in this field to find out about the lack of opportunities for artists and how they can make their careers financially viable. I think that doing both primary and secondary research will give me a good idea about everything that has already been found as well as any missing patterns.

III. RESULTS

The first interview was with Priti Patel, who was initiated into the world of dance at the age of five and received her training from eminent Manipuri dance gurus, the Late Guru Bipin Singh, and the Jhaveri Sisters. Through the rigorous training, she underwent under her Gurus, especially Smt. Darshana Jhaveri excelled as a danseuse in this form of dance and especially in the Vaishnavite Ras Leela form of the Manipuri dance tradition.

Mrs. Priti Patel said that it was her destiny and her passion for dancing that led her to become such a successful artist. Priti described her success as coming down to luck. However, she also said that artists can't make their work financially viable and especially in India, it is difficult for them to earn and make a living through it- "In India, we don't make money, it is because of our passion that we do this."

She said that a few of the most important things which can help an artist establish themselves in this competitive field are hard work, sincerity, and humility- "You have to keep learning, and learning only comes if you're humble." She said that it is extremely essential for one to accept criticism and not be arrogant and impatient.

In addition to this, she said that art is something that is done because of passion and love and not to earn an income. She agreed that all artists face different challenges and many times it is not possible for all of them to get equal opportunities and recognition. She concluded by once again emphasizing the importance of destiny- "There are many talented artists who have not made it and yet there are not so talented artists who have made it, so really it's your destiny."

My next interview was with Mr. Paresh Maity, an Indian painter. He is a prolific painter with a short career span. He has had 81 Solo Exhibitions in forty years of his career. In his early years, he did many watercolors in different locations. He gradually moved from atmospheric scenery to representations of the human form. His more recent paintings are bold and have graphic quality, with strong color and unusual cropping. His works are in several collections, including the British Museum, and the National Gallery of Modern Art, New Delhi.

He said that his success is all due to God's Grace and his sole purpose for painting is love, passion, and emotion. He said that was only seven years old when he saw artisans making idols for the festival of 'Durga Puja' in Kolkata. Their hard work and devotion are what inspired him to pursue arts as a career.

He agreed that art is an extremely competitive and challenging field and it is very rare for people to become very successful- "Every 10-15 years there is only one artist who will sustain and be a famous artist and that is a truth I have noticed. It is a very challenging field."

He said that the only reason behind his success is God's grace and blessings. He said that artists are mere tools working with love and passion. He expressed his love for art by saying- "Art is my life and my life is art. When I paint or make sculptures I think that I will make the best art by which I can bring joy and happiness to people." Moreover, he said that the only things that help people to succeed are hard work, patience, and most importantly a clear vision.

He too agreed that luck is an important factor in this field, however, all the things work together- your efforts, talents, luck, and your passion. He concluded by saying- "Hard work is the greatest wealth in life, there is no shortcut. All fields take a lot of patience and hard work and importantly your vision has to be very clear."

I also conducted two interviews with the artisans who make idols for the festival of "Durga Puja" in Kolkata. They work for several months before the festival to complete the sculptures. They both agreed that they don't get paid as much although they put in a lot of hard work, time, and effort. They said that they had been making these sculptures for about 30-35 years and they have seen their parents do the same. They said that this work gives them a lot of joy and they truly enjoy it. They added that the most important thing is working hard and doing your work well and they believe that depending upon the kind of work one puts in one can earn sufficient income and also get recognition. Furthermore, they said that their only reason for doing this was love, passion, and devotion and they would love to keep continuing this work.

IV. DISCUSSION

All the artists speak about the passion, devotion, and emotions involved in this field and their love for art. Successful artists have spoken about the importance of hard work, determination, and focus to establish themselves in this highly challenging field. They emphasize destiny and fate as important factors in achieving success. Luck emerges among all of the successful artists. They have also agreed that a lot of artists do not get proper recognition and fame and it is extremely difficult for them to make a living through their art. The literature reflects the importance of opportunities for artists and financial

viability. It talks about the lack of recognition and explores the barriers and challenges faced by artists. It highlights the fact that artists don't receive adequate income. I think this too is reflected by the fact that all of the artists have given more importance to luck rather than talent. Moreover, the artists also confirmed that they cannot depend on art for their daily income due to a lack of financial viability. Thus, the data verify the prevalence of this issue in my region and elaborate on the main themes of the literature. Both unsuccessful artists said that they put in a lot of hard work and effort, however, they don't earn as much money or respect as they deserve. Nevertheless, all artists agreed that it is their unconditional love and passion for art that keeps them going.

V. CONCLUSION

Art plays an important role in all our lives by helping us express ourselves and rejuvenating us. It acts as an effective stress reliever, having an extremely positive impact on our mental health. Artists all over the world work extremely hard to perfect their art however, both the literature as well as the data ostensibly proves that they do not get adequate income as well as recognition. It shows how art is an extremely competitive field and artists struggle all their lives to earn success. This evidence confirms the hypothesis that if artists are given more opportunities to showcase their talents, they would have a better chance at financial viability.

LIMITATIONS

This study has some limitations. One limitation of the research study is the small number of participants. According to the extent of my research I anticipated that interviewing 4 participants would help me reach the results.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Abbing, H. (2008). *Why are artists poor?: the exceptional economy of the arts* (p. 368). Amsterdam University Press. (<https://library.oapen.org/>)
- [2]. Adler, M. (2006). Stardom and talent. Handbook of economics of art and culture. (<https://www.researchgate.net/>)
- [3]. Caves, R. E. (2000). *Creative industries: Contracts between art and commerce* (No. 20). Harvard University Press. (<https://www.crb.gov/>)
- [4]. Jackson, M. R. (2004). Investing in Creativity: A study of the support structure for US artists. *The Journal of Arts Management, Law, and Society*, 34(1), 43-58. (<https://webarchive.urban.org/>)

- [5]. Kim, J., Bagla, A., & Bernstein, M. S. (2015, June). Designing creativity support tools for failure. In *Proceedings of the 2015 ACM SIGCHI Conference on Creativity and Cognition* (pp. 157-160).
- [6]. Markusen, A., & King, D. (2003). The artistic dividend. *The Art's Hidden Contribution to Economic Development. Minneapolis.*
- [7]. Markusen, A. (2006). Urban development and the politics of a creative class: evidence from a study of artists. *Environment and planning A*, 38(10), 1921-1940. (<https://www.877gethope.org/>)
- [8]. Patriotta, G., & Hirsch, P. M. (2016). Mainstreaming innovation in art worlds: Cooperative links, conventions and amphibious artists. *Organization Studies*, 37(6), 867-887. (creativemn.org)
- [9]. Yin, R. K. (2000). Case study evaluations: A decade of progress?. In *Evaluation models* (pp. 185-193). Springer, Dordrecht. (omu.edu.tr)